

SOCIAL MATURITY OF UNDER GRADUATE STUDENTS OF MATHEMATICS GROUP

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Abstract:

The sensitive side of dealing with teens, as well as some adults, has to do with social maturity. There are some signs that people choose to walk into, and there are other problems that they fall into because of immaturity. In this context, the study was conducted to find out the social maturity of under graduate mathematics group students. Social maturity means knowing what to do and striving for it by following role models to reach the desired level of acceptable social behavior. Personality comprised of pattern of feelings, thoughts, and activities that distinguishes one person from another. This study aims at investigating the social maturity of under graduate students of mathematics group. Out of the 230 respondents, 94 taken from Government College, 96 in private college and 40 from aided college were participated for the purpose of the study. Data collected was analyzed with descriptive statics using SPSS version 16. The statistical techniques used were 't' test and F est. . The results of the study indicated that under graduate students of mathematics group there exists no significant difference between gender, location of college, mode of management, medium of instruction, and year of study towards social maturity.

Key Words: Social Maturity, Distribution, Mathematics Students

Introduction:

Social maturity, like physical maturity, is often the subject of discussion among concerned adults because it can be so obvious. The five year old who reaches out to shake your hand or the eight year old who makes eye contact and says "please" and "thank you" or the twelve year old who does none of these things each is likely to earn some comment about his or her "maturity." Social maturity is, of course, a matter of experience and choice. The child who has been exposed to these finer points of etiquette (as when parents model such behaviors) and who chooses to exercise them (as when your teenager wants something), may seem socially mature.

Maturity is the ability to respond to the environment in an appropriate manner. This response is generally learned rather than instinctive. Maturity also encompasses being aware of the correct time and place to behave and knowing when to act, according to the circumstances and the culture of the society one lives in. Adult development and maturity theories include the purpose in life concept, in which maturity emphasizes a clear comprehension of life's purpose, directedness, and intentionality, which contributes to the feeling that life is meaningful. The status of maturity is distinguished by the shift away from reliance on guardianship and the oversight of an adult in decision-making acts. Maturity has different definitions across legal, social, religious, political, sexual, emotional, and intellectual contexts.

Statement of the Problem:

Social Maturity of Under Graduate Students of Mathematics Group

Need and Significance of the Study:

Social maturity achieves a three way or delta balance in our concern for the total well being of ourselves, others and the environment in which we all survive, while maintaining the individuality and importance of all. Socrates was the founder of the doctrine of an absolute morality based on the concept that happiness is the good, not of Athenians, or Spartans, or even of Greeks, but of man as man, as part of universal humanity.

Social maturity has to do with how well people understand the nature of the social world they live within. Social maturity is what enables us to function as healthy adults. Without it, we end up having a difficult time ourselves, or causing a lot of difficult times for other people. A high degree of social maturity has something to do with a high degree of social skill.

Social maturity is based on the cold hard facts of life or nature, as old as time, which we see around us every day. It goes beyond, transcends, the narrow or parochial limitations imposed by geography, nationalism, politics, religion, business, labour, law or any other segment of the overall social structure at the same time

impinging on all segments. The present study “Social Maturity of Under Graduate Students of Mathematics Group” is therefore undertaken.

Operational Definition of Key Terms:

Social Maturity:

Social maturity involves learning to properly relate to acquaintances, family, neighbors, friends, and intimate relationships. It involves understanding how to honor and respect those in authority. This can include parents, employers, or police. In this study social maturity, measure student’s maturity level in their society.

Under Graduate Students of Mathematics Group:

Students those who are studying under graduate degree (B.Sc.,) 1st year, 2nd year and 3rd year, under graduate students in science colleges and whose main subject is mathematics.

Sample Design:

In this study, the sampling unit was the under graduate students of mathematics group in Vellore district. The sample size was selected to represent the whole population and also to give the real picture. The total size of the sample was 230. The samples were collected using Random sampling technique. Out of the 230 samples, 94 were taken from government colleges, in private 96 and aided 40 were under graduate students of mathematics group taken as sample of study.

Objectives of the Study:

- To find out if there exists any significant difference between Male and Female under graduate students of mathematics group with respect to their social maturity.
- To find out if there exists any significant difference between Rural and Urban under graduate students of mathematics group with respect to their social maturity.
- To find out if there exists any significant difference between the sub samples of mode of management of under graduate students of mathematics group with respect to their social maturity.
- To find out if there exists any significant difference between medium of English and Tamil of under graduate students of mathematics group with respect to their social maturity.
- To find out if there exists any significant difference between the sub samples of year of study of under graduate students of mathematics group with respect to their social maturity.

Hypotheses of the Study:

- To find out if there exists any significant difference between Male and Female under graduate students of mathematics group with respect to their social maturity.
- To find out if there exists any significant difference between Rural and Urban under graduate students of mathematics group with respect to their social maturity.
- To find out if there exists any significant difference between the sub samples of mode of management of under graduate students of mathematics group with respect to their social maturity.
- To find out if there exists any significant difference between medium of English and Tamil of under graduate students of mathematics group with respect to their social maturity.
- To find out if there exists any significant difference between the sub samples of year of study of under graduate students of mathematics group with respect to their social maturity.

Tools Used For the Present Study:

- Social Maturity Scale by constructed and standardized by Dr. Nalini Roa’s.

Description of the Tool Used In the Present Study:

The items were scored by a five point scale. Namely strongly agree, a score of 5 is given, for agree a score of 4 is given, for neutral a score of 3 is given, for disagree a score of 2 is given and for strongly disagree a score of 1 is awarded. Higher score represent the high social maturity. The maximum social maturity score is $90 \times 5 = 450$ marks, and minimum social maturity score is $90 \times 1 = 90$ marks.

Differential Analysis:

Social Maturity of under graduate students of mathematics group

Table 1: ‘t’ test between Mean Scores of Gender of under Graduate Students of Mathematics Group towards Social Maturity

Gender	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ Value	Level of Significance
Male	91	267.92	18.43	0.411	NS
Female	139	266.87	19.46		

It is evident from the table 1 the calculated ‘t’ value is 0.411, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between male and female under graduate students of mathematics group with respect to their Social Maturity.

Table 2: ‘t’ test between Mean Scores of Location of College of Under Graduate Students of Mathematics Group Towards Social Maturity

Location of College	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	Level of Significance
Rural	104	267.81	20.07	0.385	NS
Urban	126	266.86	18.29		

It is evident from the table 2 the calculated 't' value is 0.385, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between rural and urban under graduate students of mathematics group with respect to their Social Maturity.

Table 3: 'F' Test Among the Sub- samples of Mode of management with Respect to their Social Maturity

Mode of Management	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	df	'F' Value	LOS
Between Groups	2142.616	1071.308	2	3.001	NS
Within Groups	84609.234	357.001	237		
Total	86751.850		239		

It is evident from the table 3 the calculated 'F' value is 3.001, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of mode of management with respect to their Social Maturity of under graduate students of mathematics group.

Table 4: 't' test between Mean Scores of Medium of Instruction of Under Graduate Students of Mathematics Group Towards Social Maturity

Medium of Instruction	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	Level of Significance
English	131	266.56	19.52	0.686	NS
Tamil	99	268.28	18.41		

It is evident from the table 4; the calculated 't' value is 0.686, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between English and Tamil medium of under graduate students of mathematics group with respect to their Social Maturity.

Table 5: 'F' test among the Sub - Samples of Year of Study with Respect to Their Social Maturity

Year of study	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	df	'F' Value	LOS
Between Groups	91.519	45.760	2	0.125	NS
Within Groups	86660.331	365.655	227		
Total	86751.850		229		

It is evident from the table 5; the calculated 'F' value is 0.125, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of no of siblings with respect to their Social Maturity of under graduate students of mathematics group.

Major Findings of the Study:

- It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between male and female under graduate students of mathematics group with respect to their social maturity.
- It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between rural and urban under graduate students of mathematics group with respect to their social maturity.
- It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of mode of management with respect to their social maturity of under graduate students of mathematics group.
- It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between English and Tamil medium of under graduate students of mathematics group with respect to their social maturity.
- It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of no of siblings with respect to their social maturity of under graduate students of mathematics group.

Suggestions for the Further Study:

The further study of present investigation under mentioned might be educationally beneficial.

- The present study was restricted to under graduate students it may be extended to study the social maturity of arts, medical, engineering and agriculture college students.
- The same study may be attempted with a large sample of different areas.
- The study can be replicated with another city, district and state of different age group pupils.
- The social maturity may be studied in relation to Various different variables

Educational Implication:

- Teachers will be helpful in understanding the level of development of social behaviour among the students.
- It will be helpful for college administrators to develop activities for students to develop social responsibility.
- It will help parents to develop insights to solve the social needs and problems of teenagers.

- In the study, students should be a very important level students for the development of the moral values of healthy life and the strengthening of social maturity, which will help the students.

Recommendations:

Colleges are organs of the nation's life which are ultimately responsible for the development of well-integrated, all round, wholesome personalities of their pupils physically, socially, morally, emotionally and intellectually. They have to develop moral as well as national character. The role of history students in fostering of social maturity should in no way be underestimated. They have a magnificent role to play by making use of all opportunities in and out of the college to develop the maturity. Unless the history students make conscious efforts in his direction, it will prove to be unserviceable. The history students should have themselves first try to develop their knowledge and abilities.

Conclusion:

Over the college days, the student's social maturity becomes more sophisticated, laying the foundation for adolescence. Education is an activity, which goes on in society, which develops the personality of an individual. Education develops the individual like a flower, which distributes its fragrance all over the environment. In this sense, education is that conducive, which drags a person from darkness, poverty and misery by developing his individuality in all-around development, he becomes a responsible, dynamic resou ceful and enter-praising citizen of strong, good moral character who uses all his capacities to develop his own self, his society and his nation to the highest extent by contributing his best to national honors, national glory, national culture and civilization of the nation of which he is an integral part.

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